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Learning to be an Engineer: Implications for the education system

ABSTRACT

Previous research has reframed engineering as a series of six engineering habits of mind (EHoM). This was seminal for shaping thinking around what knowledge, skills and competencies young people need to develop if the UK wants to produce more engineers. *Learning to be an Engineer* explores the ways schools can create better and more engaging learning opportunities for would-be engineers and how engineering EHoM can be integrated in the real world of busy schools and colleges. The overarching hypothesis was that, while it is necessary to continue to value disciplinary knowledge and practical skills, it is also important to think more about the dispositions engineers need to acquire. To do this, dispositional teaching and its associated learning methods were carefully considered.

The research identifies some essential elements of the signature pedagogy for engineering: the engineering design process, 'tinkering', and authentic, sustained engagement with engineers. It also describes many positive outcomes for learners taught in this way, including: increased fluency in the key habits of mind and the development of 'growth mindsets'. Additionally, it finds benefits to the capability and confidence of teachers, in particular their engagement with practising engineers.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Dispositions, signature pedagogy, education

INTRODUCTION

Learning to be an Engineer follows an earlier piece of analytic research, *Thinking like an Engineer: Implications for the education system*, which reframed engineering as a series of 'engineering habits of mind' (EHoM): systems-thinking, adapting, problemfinding, creative problem-solving, visualising, and improving [1]. The most important finding from this research is that the question, 'how do engineers think?', seemed to matter to teachers of engineering and is one which had not been discussed much previously. The teachers really engaged with this question and it was very effective at opening up discussions regarding pedagogy. Understanding more about how engineers think can assist teachers of engineering to construct appropriate curricula and select pedagogies and assessment methods which support engineering. Furthermore, understanding more about how engineers think may also provide clues as to how engineering careers can be presented more effectively to young people [1].

Drawing on extensive research and informed by discussions with experienced engineers and engineer educators, we suggested a number of signature pedagogies [2]. At the core of these is the engineering design process.

This research involves a small-scale intervention study and documents a proof of concept trial that sought to establish how schools can adopt the EHoM framework, which teaching methods are most helpful and the impact of adopting this approach.

The research began in late 2014 and was completed in summer 2016. It involved 33 schools and one further education college, 84 teachers and over 3,000 pupils. Three partners were involved in the research and each partner designed a programme of support for schools to embed EHoM using a range of different approaches.

During the research period, schools in England went through a time of considerable change, affecting their status, curriculum and accountability. A major review of the National Curriculum [3] was completed in England, which affected primary and secondary schools, as teachers engaged with, among other changes, computing as a new subject. At secondary level, the English Baccalaureate (EBacc) was introduced [4] and two new accountability measures, Attainment 8 and Progress 8, were introduced from 2016 onwards [5].

1. OUR APPROACH TO THE RESEARCH

1.1 Our theory of change

In moving from our conceptual research to a series of interventions we articulated a theory of change (TofC) in *Table 1*.

If we

- reframe engineering education to include desirable engineering habits of mind (EHoM) in addition to subject knowledge, and
- clearly articulate the principles and practices through which these EHoM can be cultivated in schools, and
- offer teachers targeted support for changing practices along with opportunities to co-design enquiries within the context of a reflective professional learning community Then
- we can better understand what school leaders and teachers need to do to change their practices to embed more effective engineering education

So that

- we can share this understanding widely and
- more effectively support the process of successful implementation of engineering education in schools

So that

- more schools embrace engineering and

- more school students have high-quality experiences of engineering education and
- more students choose to study engineering beyond school and, potentially, choose careers in engineering.

Table 1: Learning to be an engineer – a four step theory of change

Essentially we are suggesting that to overcome our current lack of engineers we need to do three things in schools:

- Move away from a focus on disciplinary knowledge (subjects such as maths) towards a better understanding of the ways engineers think and act (EHoM)
- Describe the teaching and learning methods most suited to cultivating EHoM, and
- Build teacher capability through professional development.

Our over-arching hypothesis is that while we need to continue to value disciplinary knowledge and practical skills, we also need to think more about the dispositions we want our engineers to acquire.

1.2 Research design and methods

The methodology for this small-scale intervention study was designed in line with our ToFC model. We have previously identified the six EHoM and articulated possible approaches to their cultivation [6][7]. This report builds on this and presents the outcomes of a small-scale intervention study aimed at exploring the process of implementing EHoM in primary and secondary schools, and to a lesser extent with 16 to 19 year olds in further education colleges.

The schools and college participated on a voluntary basis and their teachers engaged in a small test of change to explore how they might expand engineering in the curriculum and cultivate EHoM in their learners. The majority engaged with this as a CPD learning project for which they adopted a participatory action research approach [10], evaluating the impact of their interventions on their learners, on themselves and on their school using a number of methods.

1.3 Evaluation methods

We used a number of qualitative methods to explore the teachers' intervention experiences to ensure as much triangulation of data sources and types as possible. This involved teachers' evaluations of their action research interventions, semi-structured interviews with teachers, and qualitative feedback via a questionnaire. We adopted an appreciative inquiry approach (AI) to underpin our philosophical approach to the whole study [9].

1.4 Data analysis and reporting

To understand more about the pedagogic processes underpinning the successful cultivation of EHoM in schools and to learn more about the impact that these interventions have on learners, teachers and engineers, we used a 'realist synthesis' approach [10] to identify why the teachers' interventions worked (or did not) and in what contexts. Analysis of the data using techniques associated with realist synthesis offered the opportunity of establishing not simply 'what works' but also 'for whom' and 'under what circumstances'. This perspective, with its explanatory rather than judgmental focus, also aligned with our AI philosophy.

We used thematic analysis [11] to code the data and produced a synthesis of the ways in which teachers had cultivated EHoM. We looked for patterns, identifying issues which were frequently repeated in the data but not specific to any one sector, such as 'learning from failure' or factors associated with 'growth mindset'.

Given the short length of time during which most teachers' interventions were carried out, and the variety of locations, there are inevitably limitations on the extent to which we can generalise from our findings. However, our use of realist synthesis allows us to offer an explanatory analysis of the degree to which the different interventions did or did not work and make some general remarks about these.

2. THE STUDY

2.1 Overview

The three partners each developed a distinctive approach to using the EHoM framework but all explored pedagogies for EHoM, curriculum development and teacher professional development. All the partners encouraged teachers to use participatory action research to structure and evaluate small tests of change in classrooms. The three projects undertaken were: Thinking Like an Engineer (TLaE), Tinker Tailor Robot Pi (TTRP), and Primary Engineer in Scotland.

2.2 Thinking Like an Engineer (TLaE)

This project embedded EHoM into the curriculum in a small number of schools and a college in England. TLaE developed teachers' understanding of EHoM, supported teachers in using signature pedagogies to develop EHoM and in creating schemes of work that included EHoM across science, mathematics, computing, D&T and art, and encouraged teachers to draw on the expertise of practising engineers. TLaE involved a blend of training, school support, curriculum development and action research as part of a professional learning community.

2.3 Tinker Tailor Robot Pi (TTRP)

This project investigated the development of an ethos of tinkering within computing, D&T and the science curriculum to promote engineering and EHoM with schools in Greater Manchester. TTRP explored how a pedagogical approach to primary engineering could be established within the mainstream curriculum. TTRP encouraged the sharing of professional practice between teachers and engineers, explored how engineers work and how learning related to engineering is taught in primary schools, and identified opportunities for incorporating engineering in primary schools through science, D&T and computing.

2.4 Primary Engineer

In 2015, work began to develop one of Primary Engineer's teacher development programmes into a GTC Scotland Professional Recognition Programme in Engineering STEM Learning which is now accredited by the University of Strathclyde as a Postgraduate Certificate. This third project supported the delivery of the course aimed at primary teachers in Scotland during 2015–2016. Nine teachers from eight primary schools in Glasgow and East Ayrshire completed four assignments, one of which involved interviewing engineers to explore the growth of their EHoM.

Figure 2 below shows the key features of the three interventions diagrammatically.

Figure 2: Overview of the three project interventions

3. CULTIVATING ENGINEERING HABITS OF MIND

Four pedagogic principles guided our cultivation of effective learning habits:

1. Teachers and learners need to fully understand the habit and recognise it when it is being used successfully.
2. Teachers must create the climate for a habit to flourish, including rewarding it.
3. Teachers need to choose teaching methods that facilitate the practice and transfer of the habit.

One of the aims of our programme was to explore the value of ‘signature pedagogies’ in cultivating EHoM [2], teaching methods most likely to develop the desired engineering habits. The three elements of a signature pedagogy we explored were: the engineering design process, ‘tinkering’ (an approach to playful experimentation), and authentic learning with practitioners, such as professional engineers.

4. Teachers need to build learner engagement and commitment to the habit.

This research strongly validates the first step of our TofC. Teachers and engineers understood, approved of and used the EHoM model. They were able to connect EHoM thinking to their current practices and to the shifting external educational environment. They liked and used the signature pedagogy thinking. They responded enthusiastically to being part of a supportive professional learning community, were able to co-design different curricula using new pedagogies and were able to begin to make changes to their practices.

4. OUTCOMES FOR LEARNERS

In this section we describe the impact of teachers’ interventions on their learners. We focus on the degree to which learners were able to use EHoM, the development of engineering mindsets, impact on literacy, numeracy and oracy, on classroom management and on learners’ understanding of engineering.

4.1 Growth in learners' fluency with habits of mind Teachers observed growth in learners' fluency with the six engineering habits of mind: systems-thinking, adapting, problem-finding, creative problem-solving, visualising, and improving.

4.2 Evidence of developing engineering growth mindsets

In many cases, before the EHoM interventions, teachers said learners lacked resilience, perseverance and self-efficacy and were easily discouraged by failure, showing a fixed rather than a growth mindset. But as the project progressed, teachers reported that learners got better at using EHoM the more they practised them and that they demonstrated an increased growth mindset more generally. They also observed pupils transferring these skills in other areas of the curriculum.

4.3 Impact on literacy, numeracy and oracy

While we did not specifically aim to investigate the impact of cultivating EHoM on attainment in literacy and numeracy, some primary teachers noticed improvements in these subjects.

Teachers also reported that learners demonstrated an increased fluency in expressing ideas or opinions. Oracy, learning to talk well and learning well through talk, is regarded by many primary teachers to be of equal importance with literacy and numeracy in supporting attainment [12]. At secondary level, teachers noticed an improvement in learners' communication skills that was more employment focused. Learners demonstrated an increased confidence to network with employers and were able to talk in a more convincing manner to them when they went for job or apprenticeship interviews.

4.4 Self-managed learners and impact on classroom management

Overall, teachers reported that children were enthusiastic and motivated and that attitudes towards learning improved during the EHoM sessions. Teachers described how children had more opportunity to 'discuss, evaluate, analyse and problem solve' and that by working together on a 'level playing field' they were able to demonstrate EHoM. Some teachers found the approach took longer and noted that some more academic children found this type of learning challenging and struggled with the creating process. However, less academic children had a 'chance to shine' and demonstrate greater self-management.

4.5 Impact on learners' understanding of engineering

EHoM teaching that was reinforced through modelling by engineers enhanced learners' understanding of engineering and its potential as a career. The engineers' involvement in the curriculum showed learners how the content and skills they were learning were directly relevant to the real world.

5. OUTCOMES FOR TEACHERS

In this section we explore the impact on teachers' own habits and practices, as well as reflecting on the ways in which they engaged with engineers.

5.1 Teachers as risk takers and improvisers

It was evident that teachers found changing the habit of being 'in control of adverse events' and 'the expert' extremely difficult. Those who managed this shift found it to be very beneficial. More significant and riskier behaviour changes for teachers, such as admitting mistakes or being open-minded when receiving learners' ideas, were evidence of further development of the teachers' own growth mindset.

There were numerous occasions when teachers explained how they learnt alongside their students, particularly when they were addressing the meaning of the EHoM and attempting to transfer the use of EHoM into subjects other than engineering. They became more skilled at engaging in 'cognitive apprenticeship' style teaching techniques, such as modelling, scaffolding and coaching [13].

5.2 Teachers as collaborators

In most cases teachers were working on their interventions in pairs or groups, so had many opportunities to learn from each other. In secondary schools EHoM brought teachers from different departments together resulting in increased subject integration. Some teachers became recognised within and outside their school as 'the expert' on EHoM and on incorporating engineering into the curriculum, offering CPD sessions to their colleagues.

5.3 Teachers as reflectors

The action research approach underpinning the evaluation of the teachers' EHoM interventions encouraged them to reflect on their methods. This led to further thinking about how to adapt their traditional teaching strategies, which was most evident in two areas: their increased use of facilitation techniques and the enhancement of their questioning techniques. Teachers also became more skilled at facilitating discussion and helping learners generate ideas through good questioning.

5.4 Teachers' confidence in engaging with engineers

Though using EHoM, teachers gained knowledge that gave them confidence to make links between the subjects and skills that they were teaching and the world outside the school. Teachers' growing understanding of EHoM also appeared to increase their confidence in approaching engineers about coming into the classroom and contributing to the curriculum.

The experience encouraged curriculum managers to be more direct with employers about how their involvement with a college can be mutually beneficial. Teachers also listened to what engineers were telling them about what it is like to work as an engineer and how teaching needs to change to cultivate this style of thinking.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This series of coordinated, small-scale interventions, piloted across a number of schools in three different regions of the UK, emerged from a reframing of what it is to be an engineer and research into how teaching and learning methods can best be selected to cultivate certain EHoM. Teachers undertaking these changes were given targeted support within a wider professional learning community in which there were opportunities for them to co-design new ways of teaching. In this section we draw conclusions from our evaluation of the teachers' activities and discuss implications for different stakeholders.

Our ToC defined our overarching hypothesis that dispositional teaching using appropriate pedagogies could develop in young people the habits of mind most valuable for engineers. Furthermore, given targeted support for professional learning, teachers could adopt these pedagogies to enthuse young people about engineering.

Our findings suggest that within schools wanting to implement more engaging engineering education, the three elements of the first step of our ToC are valid:

- a) The reframing of engineering education within schools in terms of EHoM in addition to subject knowledge is something that teachers like and understand.
- b) It is possible to create the climate for EHoM to flourish at Key Stages 1, 2 and 3 using three elements of a signature pedagogy for engineering – the engineering design process, tinkering and authentic engagement with engineers – to cultivate the desired engineering habits of mind.
- c) A professional learning community that offered targeted support for teachers to design, implement and reflect on the impact of small-scale curriculum interventions in a range of different subjects did begin to change their practices.

With reference to the second step of our TofC, we have begun to better understand what school leaders and teachers need to do to embed their practices. We draw the following additional conclusions:

1. EHoM approach – With support, all schools managed to use the four-step process for cultivating EHoM, locally interpreted and adjusted according to learner age and context. The least developed EHoM was systems thinking.
2. Developing as learners – As well as acquiring more confidence and capability in the target habits, there were significant improvements in terms of mindset (perseverance, learning from mistakes, playful experimentation) and the development of confidence as independent learners. The approach produced significant improvements in learners' understanding of engineers and engineering.
3. Professional learning – The mutually supportive environment of a professional learning community coupled with supported opportunities for the designing of smallscale tests of change was helpful in enabling teachers to begin to change their habits. But even in a supportive environment, teachers found it difficult to relinquish some of their former practices.
4. Leadership – The effective cultivation of EHoM requires a school culture supportive of exploring habits of mind and using interactive pedagogies, complementary summative and formative assessment practices, practical timetabling, appropriate physical space, available local engineers, and proactivity by senior leaders. Effective school leaders recognised the commitment and investment necessary to bring about a wholesale culture change.
5. Engaging with engineers – Engineers were most effectively engaged when they had an ongoing relationship with the school, which included extended conversations with teachers, working directly with young people, hosting visits for pupils and parents in their workplaces, and participation in the professional learning of teachers. Extended contact between engineers and schools makes learning relevant and provides adult role models to convince learners and their parents of the value of engineering as a career. In terms of the third step of our TofC, we have begun to document the extent of the challenge and understand how some external changes might facilitate progress.

In terms of the fourth step we still have a long way to go. Specifically, we need to understand more about successful models of the leadership of the necessary changes required at all levels of the education system.

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